
E-LEARNING RESOURCES: IMPORTANCE IN TODAY'S SCENARIO

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Abstracts:

Teaching and learning are both factors are important in academic life of learner community. Today, learning resources have been changed as books to e-books mode and learner communities are satisfied with getting benefits more rather than traditional based resources. In this paper, researcher has highlighted the importance of e-learning resources as well as merits and demerits of it. In keeping view of objectives, author has explained the both side of these resources. In this regards, ICT has given lot of opportunity to every field including the education system.

Keywords: *Learning resources, ICT, Education system, learner community etc.*

Introduction:

Learning is natural way by which one can get information and knowledge through various ways. In the past time, the nature of learning and teaching were with traditional mode but gradually it has taken various improvement and today it has reached at the mode of online and hence the learning method has been also changed and it known as e-learning. This concept has been came from many decades but since pandemic situation it has got more importance due to critical situation arrived in the life of human being. As compared to traditional based system it has many benefits as well as some demerits. By considering the more benefits, now many education systems are going towards this path for imparting the education to e-learner community.

Teaching and learning are the basic factor of any education system. Library and learning centers are playing important role in this regards. Basically, library

organization comes close to learning component. In keeping view of current scenario's needs, it has been changed its traditional shape of learning resources into modern ways like e-books, e-journals, e-newspaper, e-references and so on. The culture of e-resources have been popularized among the learner community and moved towards such platforms for acquiring the knowledge with easy manner. In this way, E-learning resources are playing important role with different aspects in education system.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To introduce the importance of e-resources among e-learner community.
2. To explore the merit and demerits of e-learning resources.

Meaning and Definition of E-learning:

As per E-students.org, "E-learning, also referred to as online learning or

electronic learning is the acquisition of knowledge which takes place through electronic technologies and media. In simple language, e-learning is defined as e-learning is nothing but electronic based learning.”

E-learning is a new concept become more popular in digital age. Everyone is directly or indirectly is going by attaching with this platform. E-resources and e-learning are goes with hand in hand.

Without e-resources e-learning is not possible hence e-resources plays important role in e-learning education system. Since many decades, libraries have been moved towards such online databases and different type of resources platforms for providing and fulfillment of academic needs of such learner community.

Merits of E-learning Resources:

There are various benefits founds through using such type of resources. Author has highlighted on some merits as per following.

1. Save the time of learner community:

Time is very important than anything for getting success in any filed. Likewise, in the education domain there is need to save the time of learner from wasting time. This is really possible in e-learning education based system because all resources are being made available on online platform and they can search access, download or print anytime without restriction and in this way, e-learning resources can save the valuable time of the e-learning community.

2. No Physical boundaries limitation:

In traditional based learning platform, readers are need to be present at particular place physically

for getting resources through library but in the area of online e-resources platforms no need to present physical. They can access any type of resources from any place of globe. It is a great benefit to remote learner community.

3. Easy access possibility:

While acquiring any type of traditional based books from any type of library there is need to follow some process as per the rules and regulations of particular institute but in this area no need to get more restrictions as compared to traditional mode of learning platform.

4. Free from unavailability of e-resources:

Once the any resources have made in electronic form it can get perpetual nature or sustainable form. It means that such type of resources could not finish by using many times. In this view, one content can be possible to use for global community at a time. If the content is available in the electronic form and made available via online platform then no need to fear about unavailability of resources to use.

In this way, Electronic based resources which are made available on online mode can provide various merits to learner community with various aspects and it will aid to easy for doing their academic work for successful manner. Now a days, this culture have been spread with fast mode and libraries also have changed their purely traditional based nature into hybrid mode and keeping the both type of resources for fulfilling their patrons academic needs as per their demand.

Demerits of E-learning Resources:

Any coin has two sides likewise e-learning resources have merits as well as demerits. There are some demerits have explained as per below.

1. Require the electricity and Internet facility:

Without the electric power and Internet facility e-learning resources would not possible to access. This is limitation of these resources and sometimes it becomes hurdle to learner community while doing their study.

2. Eyestrain problem can create:

If the reader is always touching with online learning resources platform form it will effect on their eyes. Many studies shown that the demerit of e-learning resources while using in academic life.

3. Need to literate with basic ideas of technology:

For accessing or downloading or searching any type of e-resources to learner community is need to aware with basic tricks like searching techniques and downloading and printing information. Those are unaware regarding such tools and techniques they may or might get problem in proper accessing documents. In this way, some demerits found in the area of online

e-learning resources though various study.

Conclusion:

Information and Communication Technology has been changed and reshaped the traditional mode of working nature of each and every filed including the educational part. To keep and provide the various types of resources to their patrons is the basic duty of any type of library. In changing scenarios, libraries have been moved towards these platforms since many decades and it get speed from Covid pandemic situation. E-resources have been played valuable role in this critical situation of human being. By ignoring towards the demerits of e-resources, it has many benefits with various aspects and majority learners are still moving and getting enjoy of it in their academic life.

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